

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Dynamic lactation responses to dietary crude protein oscillation in diets adequate and deficient in metabolizable protein in Holstein cows

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Supplementary Table 2. Bodyweight regressed on experimental factors using a linear mixed model with fixed effects for cannulation status (S_j , where j = cannulated, non-cannulated), experimental period (E_k , continuous at 28-d intervals), dietary CP level (P_l , where l = LP, HP), CP feeding pattern (F_m , where m = OF, SF), and the interaction term between CP level and CP feeding pattern. We included a random intercept for and a random error term (ϵ_{ijklm} ; $n = 64$).

Fixed Effects	df	df	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>
S	1	15.05	0.272	0.610
E (linear)	1	44.15	3.728	0.060
P	1	43.18	0.330	0.569
F	1	44.38	0.000	0.984
P:F	1	43.18	0.162	0.689
Random Effects¹				
σ^2	1852			
$\tau_{00 \text{ cow}}$	3296			
ICC	0.64			
N_{cow}	17			
Observations	64			
Marginal R^2	0.036			
Conditional R^2	0.653			

¹The σ^2 and τ_{00} represent the within-cow and between-cow variances, respectively. ICC shows the intraclass-correlation coefficient for the random effect of cow.